

A 311
25 JAN 94

FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 25 10 1944 TAKE OFF 12:23/03 H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A 311
LANDING 18:36:45 Z

PROJECT OFFICER: P JONAS
AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: P JONAS/HAYLE
FLIGHT LEADER: D PERCIVAL
OBSERVER: M PITCHERING
OTHERS: C O'DOWLE
 D LAUCHLAN.
 A S WHITE

CAPTAIN: M BURGOINE
CO-PILOT: G DELMECE
NAVIGATOR: E HEATON
ENGINEER: R PRICE
LOADMASTER: H GUILTY.

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s):
OPERATING AREA: 28N 20W

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME:

FLIGHT REPORT A311 25/01/94 IPIECA/VACC

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading
12:23:03				TAKE OFF Las Palmas		
Climb to FL160		and Transit West to point			28'00N 19'44.5'W	
13:13:10 (4)	13:23:00 (5)	PROFILE P1	FL160 - 6000'	325/180	1000/min	
13:23:00 (5)	13:33:04 (6)	PROFILE P1	6000' - 50 ft	180/240	500/min	
13:33:38 (7)	13:35:39 (8)	RUN 1.1	100ft	240	K-Gamma	
13:39:30 (9)	13:41:58 (11)	RUN 1.2	100ft	060	K-Gamma	
13:42:21 (12)	13:47:26 (13)	RUN 2.1	100ft	060	L into wind	
13:47:26 (13)	13:53:15 (14)	RUN 2.2	100ft	061	L into wind	
13:56:17 (16)	14:01:21 (17)	RUN 2.3	100ft	337	L cross wind	
14:01:58 (17)	14:06:08 (18)	RUN 2.4	100ft	340	L cross wind	
14:10:46 (19)	14:15:46 (22)	RUN 3.1	2500'	145	Below cloud	
14:15:46 (22)	14:20:28 (23)	RUN 3.2	2500'	145	Below cloud	
14:22:38 (24)	14:27:59 (25)	RUN 3.3	2500'	240	Below cloud	
14:27:59 (25)	14:31:38 (28)	RUN 3.4	2500'	240	Below cloud	
14:38:15 (27)	14:41:44 (29)	RUN 4.1	6700'	090	Cloud Tops	
14:45:51 (30)	14:49:44 (31)	RUN 4.2	6700'	140	Cloud Tops	
14:49:32 (33)	14:51:28 (34)	RUN 4.3	6700'	170	Cloud Tops	
14:48:50 (35)	15:02:23 (36)	RUN 4.4	6600'	100	Cloud Tops	
15:12:03 (37)	15:15:32 (38)	RUN 5.1	4000'	165	Mid Cloud	
15:21:42 (39)	15:24:50 (40)	RUN 5.2	4100'	080	Cloud Tops	
15:28:45 (41)	15:32:02 (42)	RUN 6.1	2800'	355	Cloud Base	
15:37:49 (43)	15:40:52 (44)	RUN 6.2	3000'	065/090	Cloud Base	
15:45:31 (45)	15:48:38 (46)	RUN 6.3	3000'	345	Cloud Base	
15:57:22 (47)	15:59:39 (48)	RUN 7.1	5800'	075	Cloud Tops	
16:03:00 (49)	16:06:23 (50)	RUN 7.2	4000'	250	Mid Cloud	
16:09:16 (51)	16:12:20 (52)	RUN 7.3	3000'	090	Cloud Base	
16:16:17 (53)	16:18:19 (54)	RUN 7.4	3000'	175	Cloud Base	
16:19:38 (55)	16:20:07 (56)	RUN 7.5	3000'	360	Cloud Base	
16:28:56 (57)	16:34:15 (58)	RUN 8.1	8000'	070	L into wind	
16:34:15 (58)	16:39:19 (59)	RUN 8.2	8000'	080	L into wind	
16:41:52 (60)	16:46:56 (61)	RUN 8.3	8000'	015	L cross wind	
16:46:56 (61)	16:51:01 (62)	RUN 8.4	8000'	010	L cross wind	
16:53:39 (63)	16:56:26 (64)	RUN 9.1	6500'	180	Cloud Tops	
17:00:21 (67)	17:03:37 (68)	RUN 9.2	4000'	360	Mid Cloud	
17:07:27 (69)	17:10:40 (70)	RUN 9.3	2100'	170	Below Cloud	
17:14:14 (71)	17:17:02 (73)	RUN 9.4	2700'	005	Cloud Base	
17:20:35 (74)	17:35:15 (75)	PROFILE P2	50ft - FL080	080	500' min	
Climb to FL170		for Transit to Las Palmas				
18:36:45		LAND AT LAS PALMAS GRAN CANARIA				

Shut down position 27'56.21'N 15'22.76W

SORTIE BRIEF: 25 JANUARY 1994

IPIECA/VACC

1) SORTIE OBJECTIVE: To study the micro-physical and radiative properties of small precipitating cumulus clouds and the influence of marine aerosol on cloud micro-physics.

2) LOCATION:

3) WEATHER: Field of moderate cumulus clouds.

4) FLIGHT PATTERN:

a. Transit to operating area at suitable altitude. *FL 150 170 BACK.*

b. Execute a profile from Fl 150 to 50ft in cloud free air, if possible, @ 1000ft/min down to general cloud top then profile @ 500ft/min (30min)

c. Conduct a K-GAMMA wind field calibration (5min) @ 100ft

d. Conduct L-shaped along wind @ 100ft above sea-level and 100ft below cloud base. These runs will also be used for VACC runs. Call 2 runs on each leg, with outside MRF turn at corner.

e. If cloud is large enough and not effected by aircraft, conduct 3 figure-of-8 (centered on the cloud one leg parallel to wind and one leg perpendicular to the wind.) Leg length needs to be about 10 miles. At levels to be determined by the aircraft scientist (nominally 300 ft below cloud top, mid-cloud level and 100ft above cloud-base.)

If clouds are not distinct enough to perform above pattern, repeat L patterns at levels to be advised within the cloud layer.

f. If cloud is apparently unchanged, repeat e. ~~up to twice~~ ^{ONCE.} more, centered on the same cloud. If the cloud decays (or disappears...) repeat e. using another cloud.

g. Conduct L-shaped run above cloud top, level to be given by aircraft scientist.

h. Profile from 50ft at 500ft./min to cloud top and then transit back to base.

TOTAL DURATION

Spanis diplomatic clearance required.

5:00

TOACH.

5:40

EFF

1:30

:10

1 H

5:10

1 hour

20

1:30

A311 311

26 January 1994

Aircraft Scientists summary

Synoptic Conditions:

It was decided to fly to the South-West of the Canary Islands to the region dominated by the High pressure area towards the Azores.

Flight Summary:

A successful sortie was undertaken combining both VACC and IPIECA small cumulus flights. We had a beautiful view of Tenerife on an otherwise uneventful transit to the operational area.

We profiled into a suitable cloud field and executed two "L" patterns at 100ft above the sea surface and 100ft below cloud base. We then identified a small cumulus cloud to butterfly penetrate. due to lack of uniformity within the field it was decided not to do "L" patterns.

Although we were able to study the same cloud, location and repenetration was difficult resulting in a doubling of the estimated time.

We then chose a different cloud to do reciprocal runs on, to simplify the procedure. This worked although the short transverse runs did not succeed.

We then carried out the final "L" pattern above the cloud tops and scouted for an isolated cloud.

One was found and studied at three levels after completion of the "L" and before we profiled out of the area towards our base in Las Palmas.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. King D. Jones*

Project: *IP/CA/VACC* Date: *25/01/94*

Flight No: *A311* Page 1 of

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
<i>12:35:44</i>	<i>00</i>	<i>TRWS</i>	<i>14.7K</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>277</i>	<i>27.73</i>	<i>-15.58</i>	<i>1/8 Broken Cu. Tenerife visible Right ahead.</i>	
<i>13:13:09</i>	<i>04</i>	<i>P1</i>	<i>15.7K</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>311</i>	<i>28.02</i>	<i>-19.76</i>	<i>5/8 cu some sc clear above</i>	
<i>13:16:00</i>	<i>04</i>	<i>P1</i>	<i>11.2K</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>308</i>	<i>28.17</i>	<i>-20.02</i>	<i>clear below chunk of Cu ahead some thin S.c. clear above.</i>	
<i>13:20:45</i>	<i>04</i>	<i>P1</i>	<i>7.6K</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>283</i>	<i>28.28</i>	<i>-20.26</i>	<i>Cu below clear above slow turn to stay near cloud.</i>	
								<i>TOP @ 6000</i>	<i>mercy layer 5100ft</i>
<i>13:29:51</i>	<i>05</i>	<i>P1</i>	<i>1000</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>243</i>	<i>28.24</i>	<i>-20.42</i>	<i>4/8 cu above.</i>	
<i>13:32:05</i>	<i>06</i>	<i>P1</i>	<i>50ft</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>229</i>	<i>28.13</i>	<i>-20.54</i>	<i>3/8 st cu above broken cu to back. 1031 sea state 4/5</i>	
<i>13:33:38</i>	<i>07</i>	<i>K81.1</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>227</i>				
<i>13:35:34</i>	<i>08</i>	<i>K81.1</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>227</i>	<i>28.03</i>	<i>-20.67</i>		
<i>13:39:29</i>	<i>09</i>	<i>K81.2</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>48</i>	<i>28.05</i>	<i>-20.67</i>	<i>4/8 cu above.</i>	
<i>13:41:57</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>K81.2</i>	<i>end.</i>			<i>R</i>			
<i>13:42:22</i>	<i>12</i>		<i>100</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>28.15</i>	<i>-20.55</i>	<i>4/8 cu above.</i>	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye P. Jonas

Project: IPGCC/Vacc Date: 25/01/95

Flight No: A311

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2.20
2.5.

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:47:28	13	R1.2	100	R	48	28.29	-20.38	Sc ahead 2/8 cu above.	
13:53:13	15	R1.2	100	R		28.45	-20.13		
13:56:16	16	R1.3	400	R	326	28.45	-20.17	1/8 cu	
14:01:21	17	R1.5/1.4	100	R	311	28.66	-20.38	2/8 cu.	
14:06:00 14:08:44	18	R1.4	100	R	318	28.83	-20.53	light precipitation. Base 2700	
14:10:46	19	R3.1	2500	P	135	28.87	-20.56	hazy just at cloud base. Cu above. 2500 next level	
14:15:48	22	R3.2	2500	P	133	28.62	-20.54	1/8 cu above. 4600	
14:20:28	23	R3.2	2500	P	131	28.48	-20.19	1/8 cu above.	
14:23:58	24	R3.3	2500	P	224	28.47	-20.19	3/8 cu above very hazy.	
14:31:38	26	R3.4	2500	P.				7000 cloud top 6400 f.i.s.	
14:45:50	30	R4.2	6600	P	030	28.06	-20.78	skimming cloud top.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaya & P. Jonas

Project: IPIECA/NACC Date: 25/01/94

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
15:12:03	37	5.1	4100	P	152	27.82	-20.67	under thin Se deck Peter acting as lockout in cirrus.	
15:15:33	38	5.1	4100	P	152	27.68	-20.57		
15:21:39	39	5.2	4100	P	59	27.80	-20.71	is small in field mid level.	
15:24:50	40	5.2	4100	P		27.83	-20.53		
15:28:45	41	6.1	2900	P	348	27.73	-20.67	missed Bottom of cloud.	
15:32:02	42	6.1	2900	P		27.91	-20.74		
15:37:49	43	6.2	3000	P	378	27.77	-20.74		
15:40:53	44	6.2	3000	P					
15:45:30	45	6.3	3000	P	315	27.70	-20.70		
15:48:42	46	6.3	3000	P				climbing to 6000 to look around.	
15:57	47	7.1	5800	P	64	27.58	-21.09	TRYING another cloud / reciprocal runs.	

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
16:03:01	49	7.2	4000	P	241	27.61	-20.97		
16:06:23	50	7.2	4000	P	249	27.53	-21.13	7/8 cu same sc above.	
16:09:16	51	7.3	3000	P	73	27.53	-21.13		
16:12:20	52	7.3	3000	P				now we will try and do some short cross runs not 10 miles	
16:16:17	53	7.4	2000	P	161	27.56	-21.12	short cross runs.	
16:28:56	54	8.1	2500	P	P1	27.34	-21.10	use L to rekie lonely Cu. 16:34:14 midclm into wild legs change for VACC	
16:39:20	59	8.1	8000	P	78	27.45 27.45	-20.57	1/8 cu below	
16:41:57	60	8.3	8000	P	4	27.44	-20.63	cross wind leg hangy below 1/8 cu sc ahead.	
16:51:27								crossing over onto SC decr ^{TOPS 7500 TOPS.} 7200 4000.	
16:51:4	62	8.4	4000	P	356	27.94	-20.74		
16:53:39	63	9.1	4600	P	311	27.84	-20.69		
16:56:26	65	9.1	6600	P					

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaya & P. Tomas.*

Project: *1PIECA*
VACC
 Flight No: *A 311*

Date: *25/01/94*

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						<i>12.20.</i>	<i>74</i>		
<i>14.35.17</i>	<i>75</i>	<i>P2</i>	<i>8000</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>84</i>	<i>28 00</i> <i>-19.94</i>	<i>4/8 sc + 3/8 on clear above.</i>		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A911

Date: 25/1/96

Operator: M.P.

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONC/L	MAX SIZE	CONC/L	MAX SIZE	
1229										2D on
12500	6	0.2								IN TRANSIT @ FL 160
13000	7	0.2								
13100	6	0.2								
13135										Start P _i from FL160
13140	10	0.5								FL150
13170	12									FL140
13155	16	0.2								FL130
13165	16	0.2								FL120
13175	20	0.5								FL110
13185	40	1.0								FL100
13195	30	0.7								FL90
13203	25	1.0	0.01	5						FL80
13214	35	1.0								FL70
13224	360	3	0.5	15						FL60
13242	520	3	0.5	20						FL50
13253	570	3	0.5	20						FL40
13270	640	3	0.4	15						FL30
13283	750	3	0.5	20						FL20
13305	600	3	0.4	20						1000'
13330	700		0.4							end of P @ 50'
13338										Start K-Gamma Part 1
13340	740	3	0.4	15						
13358										end of Run
13394										Start Run K-Gamma Part 2
13400	670	3	0.4	15						
13415										end of Run

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A311 Date: 25/1/98

Operator: M

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONCL	MAX SIZE	
134221										Start Run 21 @ 100'
134300	600	3	0.4	15						
134500	620	3	0.4	20						
134700	620	3	0.4	20						
134727										end of Run
134727										Start Run 22 @ 100'
134800	560	3	0.4	12						
135000	550	3	0.4	20						
135200	490	3	0.4	10						
135315										end of Run.
135617										Start Run 23 @ 100'
135700	470	3	0.4	10						
135900	460	3	0.4	15						
140123										end of Run & Start Run 2.4 @ 100'
140200	400	3	0.3	15						
140400	400	3	0.4	20						
140607	320	3	0.4	40		11	800			end of Run
141048										Start Run 31 @ 2500'
141100	240	3	0.7	25		3				
141300	320	3	1	30						
141500	380	3	0.4	20						
141546										end of Run & Start Run 32 @ 2500'
141600	440	3	0.4	20						
141800	450	3	0.3	12						
142000	420	3	0.4	15						
142026										end of Run.
142258										Start Run 33 @ 2500'

* DRS TIME

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A311

Date: 25/1/94

Operator: MP

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/1	MAX SIZE	
142600	450	3	0.4	20						
142600	480	3	0.3	20						
142757										end of Run Start Run 3.4
142800	470	2	0.5	25						
142900	500	3	0.6	25						
143000										end of Run.
143814										Start Run 4.1
143908										enter cloud.
143934	1400	3	100	35	10	20				enter cloud
14448										end of Run
144550	60	3		5						Start Run 4.2
14										enter cloud abundant.
144725										Start Run 4.3 @ 6600'
144718	2000	3	150	35	95	30	125			enter cloud 4.3
145121										end of Run
145530										Start Run 4.4 @ 6600'
145940	2000	3	110	35	95	30	200			cloud reaching
150226	150	2	0.1	15						end of Run
151201	450	3	0.5	15						Start Run 5.1 @ 4100'
151230	1600	3	150	30	65	10	600			
151530										end of Run
152142	430	3	0.3	15						Start Run 5.2 @ 4100'
152340	1800	3	150	35	65	30	100			cloud reaching
152450										end of Run
152543	500	3	0.4	10						Start Run 6.1 @ 2500'
153050	600	3	0.5	20						
153201										end of Run

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A311

Date: 25 / 1 / 94

Operator: MP

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/P	MAX SIZE	
153749	510	3	0.8	25						Start Run 6.2 @ 3000'
153910	600	3	1.50	25	4	1	100			Cloud end of Run
154050										
154529	485	3	0.4	10						Start Run 6.3 @ 3000'
154705	600	3	1.50	30	4	1	75			cloud end of Run
154838										
155121	300	3	0.5	15						Start Run 7.1 @ 3500'
155513	1600	3	90	35	95	5	25			
155738										end of Run
160255	417	3	0.3	20						Start Run 7.2 @ 4000'
160453	2000	3	1.50	33	8	20	125			
160642										end of Run
160815	450	3	0.3	20						Start Run 7.3 @ 3000'
161059	1600	3	1.50	25	5	10	25			
161211										end of Run
161615	550	3	0.4	15						Start Run 7.4 @ 3000'
161820										end of Run
161442										Start Run 7.5 @ 3000'
161445	600	3	1.00	31	5	10				
162007										end of Run
162856										Start Run 8.1 @ 5000'
162910	10	0.5								
163100	14	0.5								
163300	27	1.0								
163415										end of Run & Start Run 8.2 @ 4000'
163600	36	0.5		5						
163800	35	2.5		5						

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A311

Date: 25/1/94

Operator: mf

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GMT	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R eff	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/1	MAX SIZE	
163120										end of Run
164154										Start Run 8.3
164200	12	0.9								
164400	20	0.5								
164600	10	0.5								
164657										end of Run & Start Run 8.4
164800	15	0.5								
165000	8	0.4								
165700										end of Run.
165339	260	0.3								Start Run 9.1 @ 6500'
165505	2000	3	150	33	10	30	100			cloud
165730										end of Run
170021	460	3	0.3	15						Start Run 9.2
170152	1800	3	75	30	8	5	200			
170340										end of Run
170726	560	3	0.4	15						Start Run 9.3 @ 2100'
171040										end of Run
171416	530									Start Run 9.4 @ 2700'
171521	550	3	100	30	4	2	175			
170768										end of Run
172036	690	3	0.6	15						Start P2
172242	550	3	0.3	12						FL10
172420	500	3	0.4	15						FL20
172554	490	3	150	35	6	15	225			FL30
172745	400	3	1	25						FL40
172934	370	3	0.4	20						FL50
173130	260	3	0.1	10						FL60

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A311

Date: 25/1/94

Operator: M P

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R eff	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/P	MAX SIZE	
173250	18	04								FL 70
173439	18	10								FL 50
173515										end of P

* DRS TIME

A311

25-JAN-94

12:41:30

001 Ω

27.76 -16.42

AS P

HDG deg T 276.	SPR mb 552.	PHGT kft 15.9	TAS knots 310.	TAT C -11.3	DEW C -28.9	WIND deg m/s 081/21
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GE DP

FWVS DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A311

25-JAN-94

13:33:06

006

Ω

28.13

-20.54

AS

P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
227.	1031.	-0.5	171.	17.0	c 9.8	066/9

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A311

25-JAN-94

17:18:00

073 Ω

27.83 -20.82

AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
235.	953.	1.7	183.	11.0	7.5	080 / 5

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT		FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A311

25-JAN-94

17:35:24

075 Ω

28.00 -19.95

AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
84.	750.	8.1	208.	4.1	-11.0	081/14

GE DP

FWVS DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A311 25-JAN-94 17:39:54 075 Ω 27.98 -19.64 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
94.	613.	13.3	258.	-5.1	-23.6	076/19

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

06Z

13

11

MAX 19.5

MIN 15.0

A311 25-JAN-94 Height time series

Run R2.2 13:47:26–13:53:15 GMT

Run R2.3 13:56:17–14:01:21 GMT

Run R2.4 14:01:58–14:06:08 GMT

Run R3.1 14:10:46–14:15:46 GMT

Run R3.2 14:15:46–14:20:28 GMT

Run R3.3 14:22:38–14:27:59 GMT

Run R3.4 14:27:59–14:31:38 GMT

Run R4.1 14:38:15–14:41:44 GMT

Run R4.2 14:45:51–14:49:44 GMT

Run R4.3 14:49:32–14:51:28 GMT

Run R4.4 14:48:50–15:02:23 GMT

Run R5.1 15:12:03–15:15:32 GMT

Run R5.2 15:21:42–15:24:50 GMT

Run R6.1 15:28:45–15:32:02 GMT

Run R6.2 15:37:49–15:40:52 GMT

Run R6.3 15:45:31–15:48:38 GMT

Run R7.1 15:57:22–15:59:39 GMT

Run R7.2 16:03:00–16:06:23 GMT

Run R7.3 16:09:16–16:12:20 GMT

Run R7.4 16:16:17–16:18:19 GMT

Run R8.4 16:46:56–16:51:01 GMT

Run R9.1 16:53:39–16:56:26 GMT

Run R9.2 17:00:21–17:03:37 GMT

Run R9.3 17:07:27–17:10:40 GMT

Run R9.4 17:14:14–17:17:02 GMT

Run P2 17:20:35–17:35:15 GMT

